

Tactile stimulation as a biomarker for positive animal welfare assessment: a systematic evaluation of current evidence and future directions

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ABSTRACT

Identifying reliable biomarkers of positive animal welfare remains a major challenge. Tactile stimulation has received increasing attention as behavioral indicator of positive affective states, because affiliative forms of touch are commonly associated with social bonding, parental care, and positive human-animal interactions. However, the extent to which tactile behaviors constitute valid indicators of positive welfare has not been systematically evaluated. In this review, tactile stimulation is assessed as a candidate biomarker for positive animal welfare assessment using established principles of preclinical animal model validation. Tactile interactions possess strong face validity because animals actively invest in them, frequently prioritize them over alternative activities, and often engage in them in situations that intuitively appear socially meaningful and affectively positive. However, physical contact itself does not uniquely specify positive affect, and the biological significance of tactile interactions may differ between interaction partners, contexts, and species. Evidence for construct validity is provided by specialized low-threshold mechanoreceptive systems, including C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents and related pathways, which are implicated in affective processing of touch and appear broadly conserved across mammals. Predictive validity is supported by evidence that tactile stimulation produces measurable effects across multiple timescales, influencing immediate behavioral and physiological responses as well as longer-term developmental outcomes relevant to welfare. In conclusion, tactile stimulation represents a biologically plausible candidate biomarker for positive animal welfare assessment, but its interpretation requires substantially greater phenotypic and mechanistic resolution than is initially assumed. The challenge for future positive welfare science may therefore not be to identify whether a behavior is positive, but to understand the biological systems, developmental histories, and ecological contexts through which that behavior acquires affective meaning.

Introduction

Animal welfare science has undergone a substantial conceptual expansion from an exclusive focus on the prevention of suffering, disease and stress to the inclusion of positive welfare states (Colditz, 2023). Contemporary frameworks define positive animal welfare as a condition of flourishing characterized by predominantly positive affective experiences alongside the development of competence and resilience (Rault et al., 2025). Although positive welfare encompasses multiple dimensions, contemporary frameworks increasingly regard positive affective experience as a central component. This shift places subjective affect at the center of welfare assessment and implies that understanding animal welfare requires access to internal experiential states rather than solely external signs of health or functioning. Because animals cannot provide verbal reports, positive affect must be inferred indirectly from behavioral, physiological, cognitive, and neural measures (Mendl et al., 2022). This reliance on indirect inference introduces a fundamental methodological challenge that is twofold: a lack of conceptual clarity and the use of context as evidence of affective valence.

First, there is a lack of conceptual clarity regarding what it means to place affect at the center of welfare assessment. In practice, this has often led to the attribution of discrete emotional states to animals based on frameworks from comparative emotion research. However, evidence from affective science in humans suggests that the relationship between subjective experience and observable indicators is neither simple nor universally consistent (Barrett, 2017). Even in humans, where verbal, subjective self-report is available, meta-analytic work does not support stable one-to-one mappings between specific emotions and physiological, neural, or behavioral signatures (Durán et al., 2021; Siegel et al., 2018; Clark-Polner et al., 2017; Touroutoglou et al., 2015; Guillory et al., 2014). Rather, emotional experiences emerge from interactions among physiological, cognitive, and environmental processes and can be expressed through multiple behavioral and physiological pathways (Barrett et al., 2017). This does not preclude the inference of affective states from observable measures, but it suggests that individual indicators should not be assumed to provide direct or unambiguous access to subjective experience.

Second, the use of context as evidence for affective valence is a challenge as well. Because affective states cannot be observed directly, researchers often infer the emotional significance of behaviors, physiological responses, and vocalizations from the contexts in which they are expressed. For example, signals produced in contexts presumed to be rewarding or aversive are often

52 assigned corresponding positive or negative emotional significance (Briefer, 2022). Although contextual information can
53 provide valuable evidence, context and affect are not equivalent. Similar situations can give rise to different affective
54 experiences across individuals due to differences in prior experience, learning history, expectations, and physiological state
55 (Barrett et al., 2017). Likewise, similar affective states may arise from different environmental circumstances. Consequently,
56 the affective significance attributed to a behavioral phenotype may reflect assumptions about the valence of the eliciting context
57 as much as properties of the phenotype itself. This creates a challenge for validating candidate indicators of positive welfare
58 independently of the conditions in which they are observed.

59 Beyond these challenges of measurement and validation lies a deeper inferential problem. By assuming that animals experience
60 emotions in forms comparable to humans (Kauvar et al., 2025; Panksepp, 2004), welfare assessment often relies on concepts
61 and interpretive frameworks derived from human affective experience. However, as Bliss-Moreau (2017) states, “*our human
62 perceptions are real. But the realness of our perceptions does not confer realness of the animals’ experience.*” Differences in
63 physiology, ecology, sensory systems, and behavioral repertoires reduce the likelihood that indicators developed in one species
64 retain identical meaning in another (Bliss-Moreau, 2017). Moreover, evidence suggests that human interpretation of animal
65 signals, including vocalizations and behavior, can be biased and inconsistent, particularly for putative positive states (Sauter et
66 al., 2010; Kiley, 1972). Consequently, while affective inference remains central to welfare science, the evidential basis for
67 linking observable phenotypes to subjective experience requires careful validation rather than intuitive interpretation alone.

68 These challenges highlight a critical limitation for progress in positive welfare science. Although numerous candidate indicators
69 of positive welfare have been proposed, the central challenge is no longer identifying additional phenotypes but establishing
70 the validity of the inferences drawn from them. Evidence that a phenotype covaries with putative positive states is not equivalent
71 to evidence that it reflects mechanisms plausibly involved in the generation or modulation of affective states. Addressing this
72 challenge requires systematic validation frameworks analogous to those used in animal model research (van der Staay et al.,
73 2009). Such frameworks evaluate whether candidate phenotypes are grounded in plausible neurobiological, physiological, and
74 behavioral mechanisms, whether they predict expected changes in welfare-relevant conditions, and whether they generalize
75 across individuals, contexts, and species. Although positive affect remains inaccessible to direct observation, systematic
76 validation can strengthen confidence that proposed biomarkers reflect biologically meaningful aspects of welfare rather than
77 assumptions about their emotional significance.

78
79 Figure 1. Conceptual framework for evaluating tactile stimulation as a candidate biomarker for positive animal welfare assessment. Face
80 validity concerns the observable and intuitive phenotype, construct validity its underlying biological mechanisms, and predictive validity
81 whether systematic changes in tactile stimulation produce expected welfare-relevant outcomes. Validation is therefore treated as a progression
82 from the intuitive and observational level, to underlying biological mechanisms, to empirical evidence linking tactile stimulation to welfare-

83 relevant outcomes. Illustrations were created by the author using AI.

84 Although tactile stimulation has increasingly been proposed as an indicator of positive welfare, evaluating this proposition
85 requires more than documenting associations between touch and favorable outcomes. The interpretation of any candidate
86 welfare assessment biomarker depends on the extent to which its relationship with the underlying construct has been validated.
87 Consequently, this review uses tactile stimulation not only as a candidate indicator of positive welfare, but also as a case study
88 through which broader questions of biomarker validation can be examined. Drawing on concepts from preclinical model
89 validation, affective neuroscience, and comparative biology, the review evaluates tactile stimulation through the
90 complementary lenses of face validity, construct validity, and predictive validity, while considering the conceptual challenges
91 involved in inferring affective states from behavior (Figure 1; van der Staay et al., 2009).

92 **Face validity of tactile stimulation**

93 Following the concept of face validity in preclinical animal models, candidate biomarkers are initially evaluated according to
94 whether they appear, on intuitive grounds, to reflect the construct they are intended to measure (van der Staay et al., 2009). In
95 the context of positive animal welfare, a candidate behavioral biomarker has face validity when the observed phenotype appears
96 consistent with behavior that would be expected intuitively in an animal experiencing a positive affective state. Because such
97 judgments rely primarily on descriptive similarity rather than evidence about the biological processes generating the phenotype,
98 face validity represents the most accessible but also the weakest form of validation. Strong emphasis on phenotypic resemblance
99 may increase confidence in a biomarker despite the absence of objective measures linking the observed behavior to subjective
100 experience (van der Staay et al., 2009).

101 Among the many behavioral phenotypes proposed as indicators of positive welfare, tactile interactions possess relatively strong
102 face validity because animals often allocate substantial time and behavioral resources toward them (Dunbar, 2010; Lehmann
103 et al., 2007). Maternal licking and grooming, allogrooming, huddling, social play, and voluntary interaction with tactile
104 enrichment devices all involve the active initiation and maintenance of direct bodily contact, often at the expense of alternative
105 activities. Dairy cattle, for example, are willing to work for access to mechanical brushes to a degree comparable to that
106 observed for feed rewards (McConnachie et al., 2018), while maternal-offspring interactions can profoundly reorganize
107 motivational systems, with lactating rodents preferentially engaging offspring-related stimuli over cocaine-associated reward
108 pathways (Febo, 2011; Ferris et al., 2005). Although such findings do not demonstrate that tactile interactions are necessarily
109 experienced as pleasurable, they contribute to the intuitive perception that certain forms of close bodily interaction occupy a
110 position of exceptional biological and motivational importance.

111 A second reason why tactile stimulation appears intuitively attractive as a welfare assessment biomarker is that many of these
112 interactions occur in contexts commonly regarded as affiliative, including offspring care, social grooming, and social play.
113 Unlike many other forms of social behavior, tactile interactions require direct physical contact between individuals. In humans,
114 social touch is closely associated with affiliation, consolation, and trust (Valori et al., 2024). Consequently, the observer's own
115 experiences with social touch may naturally inform the inferential process through which affective meaning is assigned (Barrett,
116 2017; van der Staay et al., 2009). Moreover, tactile interactions are frequently accompanied by behavioral expressions such as
117 prolonged contact, reduced vigilance, and relaxed body posture, features that contemporary positive welfare frameworks often
118 discuss alongside other low-arousal positive experiences and socio-affiliative behaviors (Rault et al., 2020). Together, the
119 sustained investment in tactile interactions, their apparent biological importance, their frequent occurrence during affiliative
120 contexts, and their outward resemblance to relaxed social engagement make tactile stimulation an intuitively compelling
121 candidate biomarker for positive welfare assessment with high face validity.

122 However, the intuitive appeal of tactile stimulation should not be mistaken for evidence that its biological significance is self-
123 evident. Superficially similar behaviors do not necessarily reflect equivalent biological, physiological, or affective processes.
124 This can be demonstrated for many social behaviors. Huddling, grooming, and maternal care all involve close bodily contact,
125 yet the adaptive consequences of these interactions may differ substantially across species and ecology. Huddling may
126 contribute to social cohesion while simultaneously reducing energetic costs through improved thermoregulation (Gilbert et al.,
127 2010). Maternal grooming in sea otters is crucial for establishing the insulating properties of the pup's fur (Zellmer et al., 2021),
128 whereas maternal licking in dogs plays an important role in stimulating urination and defecation during early development
129 (Lezama-García et al., 2019). These behaviors are all social, but the fitness-relevant consequences upon which selection acts
130 are not necessarily the same. More generally, natural selection acts on the fitness consequences of behavior rather than on the
131 specific behavioral forms through which those consequences are achieved. Consequently, similar behaviors may therefore
132 acquire different biological significance, whereas similar functional outcomes may be achieved through different behavioral
133 strategies (Barrett, 2017; van der Staay et al., 2009). Reliance on face validity alone consequently risks anthropomorphic
134 interpretation and may obscure the mechanisms that are ultimately relevant to welfare assessment.

135 Tactile stimulation illustrates this problem particularly well. Although touch is frequently associated with affiliative interactions
136 and positive welfare, the occurrence of physical contact alone provides limited information about the biological processes
137 involved. Indeed, the very features that make tactile stimulation intuitively appealing also reveal several important limitations
138 of face validity. First, physical contact itself is not inherently positive. Direct tactile interactions also occur during aggression
139 and other antagonistic, injurious, or abnormal social interactions, including tail biting in pigs, and feather pecking in chickens.
140 Moreover, the distinction between positively valenced social play and negatively valenced aggression can be difficult to infer

141 from physical contact alone, because both may involve superficially similar patterns of tactile interaction. Thus, touch per se
142 does not uniquely specify positive affect. Rather than being exclusively associated with positive welfare, tactile interactions
143 appear to recur across a broad range of biologically important social events that can be positively or negatively valenced.
144 Consequently, the occurrence of tactile interaction alone may be insufficient to infer positive affect, and its interpretation likely
145 depends on the broader biological and social context in which it occurs.

146 Second, social tactile interactions are inherently relational phenotypes. They necessarily involve at least two individuals whose
147 motivations and affective experiences may not coincide. Consequently, the biological function of a tactile interaction for the
148 initiator does not necessarily equal its affective significance for the recipient, while neither may correspond to the interpretation
149 assigned by an external observer. Barbering behavior in laboratory mice, in which one mouse plucks fur and/or whiskers from
150 another, provides an illustrative example. Barbering involves prolonged bodily contact and motor patterns that superficially
151 resemble allogrooming. As a result, the behavior may initially appear to reflect social acceptance or affiliation. However,
152 accumulating evidence has led to its recognition as a distinct abnormal behavioral phenotype associated with social dominance
153 relationships and adverse environmental conditions (Kalueff et al., 2006; Ratuski et al., 2025). From the perspective of the
154 recipient, the interaction may reflect tolerance, submission, fear, indifference, or other states that cannot be directly inferred
155 from the outward behavior alone. Thus, the key problem is not only that tactile contact can occur in negatively valenced
156 contexts, but that the same tactile event may have different affective significance for the initiator and the recipient.

157 Finally, the affective significance of tactile interactions may depend not only on whether touch occurs, but also on how it is
158 expressed. The historical distinction that emerged between allogrooming and barbering illustrates that superficially similar
159 patterns of bodily contact may ultimately require subdivision as mechanistic understanding improves. More generally, tactile
160 behaviors differ in their duration, intensity, body location, and movement across the skin, and these characteristics vary
161 substantially across species and social contexts. In humans, for example, the perceived pleasantness of touch depends strongly
162 on the dynamics of stroking (Aguirre et al., 2019; Löken et al., 2009) suggesting that tactile stimulation itself may encompass
163 multiple biologically distinct forms of interaction. Thus, broad categories such as "social touch" may ultimately prove to contain
164 multiple phenotypes that differ in their underlying biological mechanisms and affective significance.

165 Tactile stimulation therefore illustrates both the strengths and limitations of face validity as a validation criterion. Its repeated
166 association with behaviors that appear socially meaningful, biologically important, and affectively relevant makes it an
167 intuitively attractive candidate biomarker for positive welfare assessment. At the same time, neither the occurrence of touch
168 nor its outward form can establish whether the underlying biological processes are shared across individuals or species, whether
169 the interaction is experienced positively or negatively, or whether superficially similar tactile behaviors reflect equivalent
170 underlying mechanisms. Addressing these questions requires moving beyond descriptive resemblance toward evidence that
171 tactile stimulation engages biological systems plausibly involved in the generation and modulation of affective states.

172 **Construct validity of tactile stimulation**

173 The central question for construct validity is whether a candidate biomarker engages biological processes plausibly involved
174 in affective valuation. This criterion is essential because similar behavioral phenotypes can emerge from different underlying
175 mechanisms, and observation of a phenotype alone does not establish why it occurs or whether it reflects the affective processes
176 the phenotype is presumed to indicate. Construct validity therefore extends beyond demonstrating that a phenotype covaries
177 with putative positive welfare states; construct validity requires evidence that the phenotype is linked to biological processes
178 consistent with the construct it is intended to measure. As illustrated in Box 1, different mechanistic explanations of the same
179 phenotype can lead to different interpretations of welfare and, consequently, different approaches to assessment and
180 intervention. Construct validity is therefore not only a matter of conceptual precision, but also of practical relevance, as welfare
181 assessments and management decisions depend on the biological meaning attributed to observed behavior. For tactile
182 stimulation, the relevant question is whether it engages sensory and neural systems plausibly involved in the generation,
183 modulation, or representation of affective states.

Box 1. Why construct validity matters: the case of social proximity

A central challenge in welfare research is that similar behavioral phenotypes can emerge from different underlying biological processes. Social proximity provides a useful example. Individuals that remain close to one another are often interpreted as exhibiting a positive social relationship. Yet, similar patterns of proximity can arise from several distinct processes, including social reward, familiarity, herd cohesion, reduced vigilance demands, avoidance of isolation, or attraction to shared resources. Although these mechanisms produce comparable observable outcomes, they imply different underlying biological processes (equifinality) and may therefore support different interpretations of the phenotype.

Consequently, observation of a phenotype alone does not establish why it occurs. Importantly, this uncertainty extends beyond interpretation. If proximity within a species reflects partner-specific social reward, welfare interventions may need to prioritize maintaining particular social bonds. For example, during regrouping or weaning in pigs, this interpretation would imply that familiar or preferred pairings should be identified and preserved where possible, rather than assuming that any conspecific provides equivalent social support. In contrast, if proximity in a species primarily reflects the benefits of group cohesion or social buffering, welfare may depend more on maintaining access to conspecifics in general, even if specific dyads are not preserved. Thus, different mechanistic explanations of the same phenotype can lead to different conclusions regarding welfare assessment, intervention design, and management practices.

Construct validity addresses this challenge by evaluating whether a candidate biomarker is grounded in biological processes

plausibly involved in the generation or modulation of affective experience. The same principle applies broadly to proposed indicators of positive welfare, including play, vocalizations, social interactions, and tactile stimulation.

184 A useful starting point is the observation that sensory systems can contribute differently to discriminative and affective aspects
185 of perception. Nociception, the neural detection and processing of potentially tissue-damaging stimuli that may contribute to
186 aversive experiences such as pain, provides a well-characterized example. In the skin, fast-conducting myelinated A δ afferents
187 primarily convey rapid information about the location and intensity of potentially damaging stimuli. For instance, contact with
188 a hot surface can trigger withdrawal of the affected body part, thereby limiting tissue damage. By contrast, slower unmyelinated
189 C-fibers contribute more strongly to the affective and motivational dimensions of pain. These fibers do not simply provide
190 additional sensory detail; they help determine how aversive, salient, and behaviorally significant the stimulus is. For example,
191 following tissue damage, C-fiber-mediated input can contribute to the unpleasantness of pain and thereby promote guarding of
192 the injured area, avoidance of similar stimuli, and longer-term changes in motivation and learning (Talbot et al., 2019; McGlone
193 & Reilly, 2010). Although this distinction is not absolute, it illustrates how sensory pathways can be specialized for functions
194 extending beyond stimulus detection alone. A similar organizational principle has been proposed for touch, in which fast-
195 conducting A β afferents primarily encode the discriminative properties of tactile stimuli, such as pressure, texture, vibration,
196 and spatial detail, whereas slower-conducting C-tactile afferents are thought to preferentially signal their affective qualities
197 (Pitcher et al., 2016).

198 C-low threshold mechanoreceptors are a specialized class of unmyelinated sensory neurons located in hairy skin that respond
199 optimally to slow, gentle stroking delivered at skin temperature (Moore et al., 2025; Ackerley et al., 2014a; Löken et al., 2009).
200 Unlike A β afferents, which primarily encode discriminative features of touch, C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents
201 exhibit response properties consistent with a role in processing gentle, slow, dynamic tactile stimulation. In humans, activation
202 of these fibers is reliably associated with subjective ratings of pleasantness, with stroking velocities that maximize C-low
203 threshold mechanoreceptor firing also producing the highest pleasantness ratings (Löken et al., 2009). Additional evidence
204 comes from clinical dissociations. A rare patient lacking functional large myelinated A β afferents but retaining C-fiber function
205 preserved the ability to experience the pleasant aspects of gentle stroking despite profound deficits in discriminative touch
206 (Olausson et al., 2002). Conversely, stimulation of skin regions with sparse C-low threshold mechanoreceptor innervation, such
207 as glabrous skin of the palm, is associated with reduced pleasantness ratings compared with skin regions with a rich C-low
208 threshold mechanoreceptor density (Ackerley et al., 2014b; McGlone et al., 2012). These findings support the existence of a
209 tactile pathway specialized for affective rather than purely discriminative aspects of touch.

210 The relevance of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents to animal welfare depends on whether this pathway extends
211 beyond humans. Although direct cellular homology across species remains incompletely resolved, evidence accumulated across
212 mammals suggests the presence of specialized low-threshold unmyelinated mechanoreceptors with remarkably similar
213 anatomical, physiological, and functional properties (Körner et al., 2025; Morrison et al., 2010). C-low threshold
214 mechanoreceptor-like afferents have been identified in a range of mammals, including rodents, rabbits, cats, nonhuman
215 primates, and pigs (reviewed in Pitcher et al., 2016). Despite species-specific differences in skin morphology and ecology,
216 these afferents share key anatomical and physiological characteristics, including unmyelinated morphology, low mechanical
217 thresholds, and preferential responsiveness to gentle stroking stimuli (Vrontou et al., 2013; Obreja et al., 2010; Olausson et al.,
218 2010). This conservation suggests that affective touch is not a uniquely human phenomenon, but may reflect a broader
219 mammalian sensory system. However, the presence of homologous afferents alone does not establish their functional
220 significance. Construct validity therefore requires determining whether activation of this pathway engages neural systems
221 involved in affective valuation and motivational processing in nonhuman animals.

222 Evidence for construct validity becomes stronger if activation of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents engages neural
223 systems involved in affective valuation and reinforcement. Experimental studies in rodents indicate that gentle, non-noxious
224 tactile stimulation increases dopamine release within the nucleus accumbens through signaling pathways involving the ventral
225 tegmental area, a core component of mesolimbic reward circuitry, whereas noxious stimulation does not produce the same
226 response (Maruyama et al., 2012; Morales & Margolis, 2017). More direct evidence comes from causal manipulations of C-
227 low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents. Optogenetic activation of these neurons is sufficient to induce dopamine release in
228 the nucleus accumbens, while genetic ablation abolishes this response (Elias et al., 2023). Importantly, activation of this
229 pathway also produces behavioral consequences consistent with positive valuation. Both naturalistic tactile stimulation and
230 direct activation of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents support conditioned place preference, indicating that stimulation
231 is assigned positive value and can drive approach behavior (Vrontou et al., 2013; Huzard et al., 2022; Elias et al., 2023).
232 Together, these findings suggest that C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents activation engages neural systems involved
233 in reward processing and reinforcement, providing a mechanistic link between tactile stimulation and processes plausibly
234 involved in affective valuation. Importantly, these findings demonstrate that tactile stimulation engages neural systems
235 involved in assigning value to stimuli, rather than merely encoding their physical properties, supporting the hypothesis that
236 affective touch constitutes a distinct functional domain of somatosensory processing.

237 Additional support for construct validity comes from the anatomical organization of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents
238 and the distribution of social touch across the body. If these afferents contribute to affective touch processing, variation in their
239 density should have functional significance rather than being randomly distributed. Consistent with this prediction, high-
240 resolution mapping studies in mice have identified elevated densities of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents in regions
241 such as the shoulders and back (Liu et al., 2007). Similar proximal–distal gradients have been reported in other mammals,

242 including cats and nonhuman primates (Bessou & Perl, 1969; Kumazawa & Perl, 1977), with additional evidence indicating
243 greater C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferent innervation in proximal compared with distal nerves (Delfini et al., 2013).
244 Functional studies suggest that this anatomical specialization is biologically relevant. In rodents, tactile stimulation of C-low
245 threshold mechanoreceptor afferents-rich regions evokes stronger dopamine release in the nucleus accumbens than stimulation
246 of more sparsely innervated areas (Maruyama et al., 2012). Furthermore, recent high-resolution mapping of social touch
247 interactions in rats demonstrated that tactile contact is not distributed randomly across the body but occurs preferentially in
248 specific regions, including areas characterized by elevated C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents density (Klibaite et al.,
249 2025). Together, these findings suggest that the anatomical organization of the C-low threshold mechanoreceptor system
250 corresponds to biologically meaningful patterns of tactile interaction, consistent with a specialized role in processing socially
251 relevant touch.

252 Although much of the mechanistic understanding of affective touch has emerged from tractable laboratory species, evidence
253 supporting similar organizational principles is beginning to emerge in livestock. C-low threshold mechanoreceptors have been
254 identified in pigs (Körner et al., 2025; Hirth et al., 2013), and studies indicate that tactile interactions are not behaviorally inert,
255 but can modify behavioral, physiological, and neural responses in recipient animals (Schmitt et al., 2025; Högberg et al., 2025;
256 Truong et al., 2024). Moreover, recent work demonstrates that tactile interactions in pigs are distributed across the body in a
257 structured rather than random manner (Högberg et al., 2025), paralleling observations from rodent models (Klibaite et al.,
258 2025). Interestingly, an important but largely unexplored question is whether species variability in affiliative tactile behavior
259 correspond to differences in the mechanical stimulation delivered to the skin. Current models of C-low threshold targeted touch
260 have largely been informed by species whose affiliative interactions involve slow, gentle, and repetitive movements across the
261 skin, such as rodents, cats, monkeys and humans. The affiliative tactile repertoire of pigs, however, appears to exhibit different
262 spatiotemporal dynamics, relying predominantly on active snout-mediated contact (Camerlink & Turner, 2013). Whether these
263 distinct patterns of tactile stimulation in pigs engage comparable affective touch mechanisms remains an important open
264 question.

265 Additional support for construct validity comes from the role of tactile interactions in social regulation and development across
266 mammals. In many social species, tactile behaviors appear to serve functions extending beyond their immediate physical
267 consequences. For example, some primate species devote a substantial proportion of their daily activity budget to grooming
268 and allogrooming, far exceeding that required for hygienic maintenance alone, suggesting that these behaviors have important
269 social functions (Dunbar, 2010; Lehmann et al., 2007). Maternal care similarly relies heavily on tactile interactions such as
270 licking, grooming, and close physical contact, which influence offspring development, physiological regulation, and social
271 bonding. In rodents, variation in maternal tactile care exerts long-lasting effects on stress responsiveness, cognition, and social
272 behavior through epigenetic mechanisms acting during sensitive developmental periods (Kaffman and Meaney, 2007; Bagot et
273 al., 2012). Tactile interactions also contribute to social buffering, with unstressed individuals increasing allogrooming toward
274 stressed conspecifics, thereby reducing anxiety-like behavior (Burkett et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2021). More broadly, these
275 findings suggest that tactile interactions are repeatedly recruited in biological contexts involving social regulation, attachment,
276 and stress resilience, rather than serving exclusively hygienic or discriminative functions. In humans, the characteristics of
277 touch appear to be similarly important. Parents spontaneously stroke infants at velocities closely matching the optimal response
278 properties of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents, and C-low threshold mechanoreceptor-targeted stroking is associated
279 with enhanced regulation of infant distress (Croy et al., 2016; Bytowski et al., 2020). Together, these findings indicate that
280 tactile interactions are embedded within conserved biological systems involved in social regulation and affective modulation,
281 consistent with the hypothesis that tactile stimulation contributes to affective processes rather than serving solely discriminative
282 or hygienic functions. Evidence from both humans and nonhuman animals indicates that factors such as prior experience, social
283 context, the identity of the interaction partner, and the degree of agency over the interaction can modify responses to otherwise
284 similar tactile stimuli (Stevens et al., 2024; Truong et al., 2024; Carra et al., 2014), suggesting that affective touch is shaped by
285 the interaction between sensory processing and higher-order social and cognitive mechanisms.

286 Despite this mechanistic evidence, activation of C-low threshold mechanoreceptor afferents cannot be equated directly with
287 positive welfare. Much of the evidence reviewed above demonstrates engagement of neural systems involved in reward
288 processing, reinforcement learning, and motivational salience. However, these systems are not uniquely associated with
289 positive welfare states. For example, elevated activity within mesolimbic dopaminergic pathways and increased responsiveness
290 to rewarding stimuli are also observed in pathological conditions such as mania in both humans and animal models (Kristensen
291 et al., 2018). More generally, neural signatures associated with reward processing may reflect multiple functional states that
292 differ in their affective quality and welfare significance. Consequently, activation of reward-related circuitry should be viewed
293 as evidence supporting the construct validity of tactile stimulation rather than as proof that the resulting experience is
294 necessarily positive. Construct validity can strengthen the biological plausibility of a biomarker, but it cannot eliminate the
295 broader inferential gap between measurable processes and subjective experience.

296 **Predictive validity of tactile stimulation**

297 Although construct validity can establish that tactile stimulation engages biological systems plausibly involved in affective
298 processing, it does not determine whether variation in tactile interactions is associated with meaningful changes in the organism.
299 Addressing this question requires consideration of predictive validity. Predictive validity ultimately requires demonstrating that
300 variation in a candidate phenotype systematically reflects variation in the underlying construct (van der Staay et al., 2009). For
301 tactile stimulation, this requires understanding not only whether tactile behavior predicts welfare-relevant outcomes, but also

302 whether the biological systems hypothesized to confer affective significance are actually involved.

303 A first observation emerging from the literature is that tactile stimulation is rarely behaviorally or physiologically inert. Across
304 species, tactile interactions are associated with measurable changes in the animals receiving them. In sheep, stroking by a
305 familiar caregiver reduces heart rate, increases heart-rate variability, and alters behavioral responses toward the caregiver
306 (Coulon et al., 2015). In cattle, access to mechanical brushes modifies grooming behavior, feeding patterns, and behavioral
307 allocation, while also influencing physiological and production-related measures (DeVries et al., 2007; Velasquez Muñoz et
308 al., 2019; Li et al., 2024). Similarly, tactile interactions in pigs and cattle reduce avoidance of humans, increase voluntary
309 approach behavior, and influence physiological measures associated with stress regulation (Probst et al., 2012; Probst et al.,
310 2013; Tallet et al., 2014; Wredle et al., 2022). Although the interpretation of these effects is not always straightforward, the
311 consistent observation across studies is that manipulating presence of a specific tactile experience can alter behavioral and
312 physiological functioning.

313 Importantly, the consequences of tactile stimulation are not restricted to immediate responses. Repeated tactile interactions can
314 produce effects that persist long after the interaction itself has ceased. In pigs, repeated stroking and scratching after weaning
315 alters subsequent interactions with humans, with treated animals approaching handlers more rapidly and spending more time
316 in close proximity to them days to weeks after the tactile interactions have ceased (Tallet et al., 2014). In beef cattle, variation
317 in early-life tactile experience predicts later responses to humans, with calves receiving gentle tactile stimulation shortly after
318 birth exhibiting reduced avoidance and less stress-related behavior during handling and slaughter months later (Probst et al.,
319 2012). Such findings suggest that tactile stimulation can exert lasting effects on how animals interact with their physical and
320 social environment.

321 Particularly compelling evidence comes from developmental studies demonstrating that variation in tactile experience predicts
322 long-term behavioral, physiological, and neurobiological outcomes. In prairie voles, naturally occurring variation in parental
323 tactile contact influences offspring stress responsiveness, aggression, and patterns of brain connectivity, while maternal licking
324 and grooming in rats exerts lasting effects on cognition, social behavior, exploratory tendencies, and stress reactivity through
325 epigenetic mechanisms acting during sensitive developmental periods (Perkeybile and Bales, 2015; Seelke et al., 2016; Bagot
326 et al., 2012; Caldji et al., 2000; Kaffman and Meaney, 2007). Convergent evidence in humans indicates that tactile interactions
327 contribute to attachment, physiological regulation, and neurodevelopment. Maternal stroking moderates the association
328 between prenatal depression and later negative emotionality in infants (Sharp et al., 2012), while tactile interventions during
329 early development have been associated with improvements in developmental outcomes in premature infants (de Róiste, 2004).

330 These observations are notable because many of the affected outcomes extend beyond immediate affective responses.
331 Contemporary frameworks increasingly conceptualize positive welfare as a condition of flourishing characterized not only by
332 positive affective experiences but also by the development of competence and resilience (Rault et al., 2025). Several of the
333 reported consequences of tactile stimulation, including altered stress responsiveness, changes in social behavior, developmental
334 calibration of physiological systems, and responses to novel or challenging situations, are therefore relevant not only to affective
335 state but also to the broader processes through which animals cope with and adapt to their environments.

336 At the same time, important limitations remain. The consequences of tactile stimulation are not always consistent across studies,
337 with some investigations reporting limited, transient, or context-dependent effects (Hayes et al., 2021; Griffin et al., 2024).
338 Accumulating evidence suggests that outcomes depend not only on whether tactile stimulation occurs, but also on
339 characteristics of the interaction itself, including body location, movement across the skin, duration, familiarity of the
340 interaction partner, social context, developmental history, and prior experience (Aguirre et al., 2019; Bytowski et al., 2020;
341 Croy et al., 2016). Such findings suggest that tactile stimulation should not be treated as a unitary phenomenon and raise the
342 possibility that apparently conflicting results may reflect differences in the biological stimulus being delivered.

343 A further challenge for establishing predictive validity is that no single species currently allows simultaneous access to all
344 levels of analysis required for validation. Predictive validity ultimately requires demonstrating that variation in tactile behavior
345 reflects biologically meaningful variation in the processes relevant to welfare. Human studies provide unique insight into the
346 affective significance of tactile stimulation but are constrained in the degree to which underlying mechanisms can be
347 experimentally manipulated. Rodent models permit mechanistic investigation of sensory pathways and causal testing of
348 hypotheses but provide more limited access to subjective experience. Livestock studies offer direct relevance to animal welfare
349 assessment yet have largely focused on phenotypic and welfare-related outcomes without equivalent mechanistic
350 characterization. Consequently, evidence linking tactile phenotypes, underlying biological mechanisms, affective significance,
351 and welfare-relevant outcomes remains fragmented across species and disciplines. As a result, it remains difficult to determine
352 whether observed changes in tactile behavior reflect variation in the biological systems hypothesized to underlie affective touch,
353 whether activation of these systems causally contributes to welfare-relevant outcomes, or whether apparently similar tactile
354 interactions operate through common mechanisms across species and contexts.

355 Taken together, the available evidence suggests that tactile stimulation possesses moderate predictive validity. Variation in
356 tactile experience is associated with systematic changes in behavioral, physiological, social, and developmental outcomes
357 across species, indicating that tactile interactions engage processes relevant to affective regulation, competence, and resilience.
358 However, predictive validity remains incomplete because the biological mechanisms linking tactile phenotypes to welfare-
359 relevant outcomes remain insufficiently characterized. Consequently, current evidence supports tactile stimulation as a
360 promising candidate biomarker within positive welfare assessment, while highlighting the need for studies that explicitly

361 connect tactile behavior, underlying biological systems, and welfare-relevant outcomes within the same experimental
362 framework.

363 **Future directions**

364 Future research should move beyond treating tactile stimulation as a binary intervention and instead characterize the
365 multidimensional parameter space through which tactile interactions acquire affective significance. Current evidence suggests
366 that tactile stimulation should not be considered a unitary phenomenon, but rather a stimulus varying in physical characteristics
367 such as velocity, pressure, temperature, body location, duration, and movement across the skin (Klibaite et al., 2025; Ackerley
368 et al., 2014a; Löken et al., 2009). Human and rodent studies indicate that these parameters strongly influence the engagement
369 of specialized C-low threshold mechanoreceptive systems, providing a biologically plausible framework for identifying
370 dimensions that contribute to affective valuation. At the same time, emerging evidence from livestock suggests that animals
371 may discriminate between different forms of tactile interaction, while showing substantial individual variation rather than a
372 universal preference for a single mode of contact (Amann et al., 2025). Such findings further support the view that tactile
373 stimulation should not be conceptualized as a single homogeneous stimulus. However, whether particular combinations of
374 these characteristics preferentially evoke positive, neutral, or negative affective states remains largely unknown, especially in
375 livestock species. Future work should therefore aim to define species-specific, context-specific, and potentially individual-
376 specific affective parameter spaces for tactile stimulation, rather than assuming that a single pattern of touch generalizes across
377 taxa. Such an approach would parallel established principles in sensory ecology, where species differences in visual, auditory,
378 and olfactory systems are routinely considered when interpreting behavior (Burnett, 2011; Endler, 1992).

379 An additional challenge is that tactile stimulation encompasses multiple classes of interaction, including naturally occurring
380 social touch between conspecifics, forced interactions between conspecifics by overcrowding, human-animal tactile
381 interactions, and non-social forms of tactile enrichment such as mechanical brushes. Although these forms of stimulation may
382 engage overlapping sensory pathways, their biological functions and affective significance are unlikely to be identical. Future
383 work should therefore determine the extent to which findings obtained in one domain generalize to the others and identify the
384 conditions under which different sources of tactile stimulation engage common affective mechanisms.

385 A broader and largely unexplored challenge is that the biological systems underlying affective touch may themselves be
386 developmentally plastic. Evidence from rodents, non-human primates, and humans demonstrates that early tactile experiences
387 exert long-lasting effects on stress regulation, social behavior, and brain development, with maternal tactile interactions shaping
388 neurodevelopment through behavioral epigenetic and genetic mechanisms (Meaney, 2001; Champagne and Meaney, 2007;
389 Bagot et al., 2012; Nelson et al., 2014). Accumulating evidence suggests that the affective consequences of tactile interactions
390 depend not only on their physical properties but also on prior social experience (Stevens et al., 2024), raising the possibility that
391 the biological significance of affiliative touch is itself partly calibrated during development.

392 If the affective significance of tactile interactions is partly calibrated through experience, then variation in developmental
393 history may become a source of variation in how tactile behavior should be interpreted. This possibility introduces an important
394 conceptual challenge for animal welfare science. Biomarker validation generally assumes that the biological processes
395 underlying a phenotype are sufficiently stable that the same observable behavior carries a similar interpretation across
396 individuals and populations. However, if affective touch systems are partly shaped by early social experience, welfare
397 assessment may involve not only measuring the current state of an animal, but measuring that state relative to the developmental
398 environment that produced it. Commercial dairy production systems may provide a particularly informative natural experiment
399 in this regard, as maternal separation typically occurs within hours after birth and the offspring subsequently rear the next
400 generation under the same management conditions. Evidence from rodents suggests that aspects of maternal behavior and stress
401 responsiveness can propagate across generations through social and epigenetic mechanisms (Champagne and Meaney, 2007).
402 Although entirely speculative at present, it therefore remains unknown whether repeated disruption of species-typical tactile
403 and social interactions influences not only immediate welfare outcomes but also the biological systems through which later
404 tactile interactions acquire affective significance. If so, superficially similar tactile behaviors observed across populations, for
405 example between dairy and beef cattle, may not necessarily reflect identical underlying affective or motivational processes.
406 Resolving these questions will likely require integrative research programs that combine mechanistic studies in experimental
407 models with welfare-oriented research in livestock species. No single species currently provides simultaneous access to all
408 levels of analysis required for validation, highlighting the need for comparative and translational approaches.

409 A final challenge concerns the broader framework through which positive welfare is assessed. The present review illustrates
410 that tactile stimulation, despite its relatively strong mechanistic foundation, remains subject to important contextual,
411 developmental, and individual sources of variability. Rather than representing a limitation specific to tactile interactions, this
412 may reflect a more fundamental property of positive welfare itself. An additional challenge is that affective states are not
413 directly observable and must therefore be inferred. Human studies suggest that individuals differ substantially in their ability
414 to distinguish and describe their own affective experiences and that these differences are associated with variation in how
415 accurately they infer the emotional states of other humans (Israelashvili et al., 2019; Erbas et al., 2016). Although the
416 mechanisms underlying this relationship remain debated, these findings suggest that affective perception depends not only on
417 the observed individual but also on the conceptual framework through which observations are interpreted. Comparable evidence
418 remains limited in animals, but the possibility that observer characteristics influence the interpretation of animal behavior
419 warrants consideration. This perspective further emphasizes the need for validation frameworks that rely on converging

420 behavioral and biological evidence rather than intuitive interpretation alone.

421 A useful parallel can be drawn with preclinical behavioral neuroscience, where complex constructs such as anxiety, sociability,
422 or cognitive function are rarely inferred from a single behavioral assay (Crawley, 2007). Instead, these domains are evaluated
423 using batteries of complementary tests that capture different aspects of the underlying construct, and conclusions emerge from
424 the convergence of multiple partially independent observations. Future developments in animal welfare science may benefit
425 from adopting a similar perspective. Emerging technologies, including computer vision, automated behavioral tracking, and
426 machine audition, provide unprecedented opportunities to quantify the spatial, temporal, and social dynamics of tactile
427 interactions. Rather than searching for a single definitive biomarker of positive welfare, these approaches could facilitate the
428 integration of tactile behavior with vocal communication, social networks, locomotion, physiology, and other indicators into
429 multidimensional models of affective state. In this framework, tactile stimulation would not necessarily serve as a standalone
430 measure of positive welfare, but as one component of a broader biologically informed battery of complementary biomarkers.

431 Conclusion

432 The evidence reviewed here suggests that tactile stimulation occupies a distinctive position among candidate indicators for
433 positive welfare assessment. Unlike many proposed behavioral biomarkers, tactile stimulation can be examined across multiple
434 levels of biological organization, from observable behavior to peripheral sensory systems, neural mechanisms, developmental
435 processes, and welfare-relevant outcomes. Although important gaps remain, this multilevel framework provides a unique
436 opportunity to evaluate face validity, construct validity, and predictive validity within a common biological context. The
437 challenge for future positive welfare science may therefore not be to identify whether a behavior is positive, but to understand
438 the biological systems, developmental histories, and ecological contexts through which that behavior acquires affective
439 meaning.

440 At the same time, the present review highlights that mechanistic plausibility should not be confused with mechanistic certainty.
441 The affective significance of tactile interactions appears to depend not only on the occurrence of touch itself, but also on its
442 physical characteristics, social context, developmental history, and the biological state of the individuals involved. Moreover,
443 the same observable tactile phenotype may not necessarily reflect identical underlying mechanisms across species, populations,
444 or even interaction partners. Consequently, tactile stimulation should not be regarded as a universal or self-evident marker of
445 positive welfare, but as a biologically grounded phenotype whose interpretation requires careful validation.

446 More broadly, this perspective suggests that progress in positive welfare science may depend less on identifying single
447 definitive behavioral indicators than on understanding the biological systems from which such phenotypes emerge. Rather than
448 asking whether touch is inherently positive, future research should determine which forms of tactile interaction, under which
449 circumstances, and for which individuals engage affective systems in ways that are relevant to welfare. In this regard, tactile
450 stimulation may serve not only as a promising candidate biomarker, but also as a model system for developing a more
451 mechanistically informed science of positive animal welfare.

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